

Reclaiming the Metamorphic Imagination: Ecosomatic Practice and the Poetics of Myth in the Age of Ecological Disaster (extended version)

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Abstract

How can we approach the heritage of Peter Brook's performative engagement with other worlds in the shadows of anthropogenic ecological disasters? The article performs a poetic and theoretical dialogue between ecosomatic and dramaturgical pedagogical practices. Our aim is to expose the wounds of separation between nature and civilization and the inability to grieve for ecological losses that pervades contemporary society. We are called to approach the training of the imaginal and physical world of the performer through the recollection of an ancient solidarity with the nonhuman and with matter and through an engagement with our mythic cultural heritage. The space we are interrogating to understand how to become eco-embodied artists lies outside of theatres, and it is not empty: it is where the river passes, where the dunes begin, where the bark pulverises - a theatre physically not yet revealed to human cognition that works through processes of care, response-ability, and cultural resistance. The text feeds on the lived experience of *La Selva*, a participatory ecosomatic and regenerative arts residency held in the Natural Reserve of the Roman Coast (Rome, Central Italy) in October 2023. *La Selva* (literally, the forest) is explored as an emergent order of radical relationality that foregrounds the metamorphic thresholds between life and death constituting a key topos in Greek myth. This trespassing into the mythic announces a movement of social inclusion and civic resurgence.

Keywords: ecosomatics; dramaturgy; poetics of myth; metamorphosis; performer training; becoming sensors; hapticity; non-anthropocentric creative ecologies; participation; creative collaboration.

Introduction

More than half a century after ground-breaking director Peter Brook delivered the four lectures then published as *The Empty Space*, we could ask again: what is the space of theatre? Is this space still empty? Where is this space? This article performs a poetic and theoretical dialogue between ecosomatic and dramaturgical training practices. We are called to approach the training of the imaginal and physical world of the performer through the recollection of an ancient solidarity with the nonhuman and with matter and through an engagement with our mythic cultural heritage. Our aim is to expose the wounds of separation between nature and civilization and the inability to grieve for ecological losses that pervades contemporary society. We want to draw attention to how the culture of theatre can confront the tragedy of our destructive cultural heritage and recover the capacity to grieve for the ecological losses we have caused.

In this article and in the creative collaborative practice on which it is based, we posit the need for a methodology that engages bodies to enter the issue of ecological wounds. The article is structured as a dialogue between the authors guided by a series of questions through which we dig into our practice and scholarship and try to weave threads between our different approaches and vocabularies of creative research.¹ We have entered the horizon of a thought that reveals how we are not environmental and ecological and how scandalous the separation from the rest of nature is. Separation ultimately means the refusal to feel the ecological disaster as impending, as the accident that is about to overwhelm us. It is from the point of view of this refusal that the question of drama and myth and the power of words burst onto the scene. The space we are interrogating to understand how to become eco-embodied artists lies outside of theatres: it is where the river passes, where the dunes begin, where the bark pulverises. It is a theatre that is millions of years old, in motion from its origins, expanding and rotating, cosmically attuned, physically not yet revealed to human cognition.

¹ The creative dialogue between the authors began in 2021 with the collaboration at Humanitas Mundi Teatro, a nascent ensemble of performance research and cooperation based in Rome, and was then furthered through the development of *Ecosomatic Persephone*, a performance lecture presented at the 9th Conference of the International Platform for Performer Training (IPPT), held in Chiusi (Italy), 12-15 January 2023. Thereafter the dialogue was based on a collaboration with Teatro del Lido di Ostia, a public participatory theatre established on the periphery of Rome in 1992, <https://www.teatriincomune.roma.it/teatro-del-lido-di-ostia/>.

In *The Empty Space* Peter Brook addresses a humanity still troubled by the atrocities of the two World Wars, denounces the culture of representation and praises theatre artists who still acknowledge “that the world of appearance is a crust... under the crust is the boiling energy we see if we peer into a volcano”.² Through his poetical history of mankind, and particularly in the *Mahabharata*, Brook has intimately approached a way of feeling the other world through a story-worlding performative practice. His work leaves us with radical questions about gesture, about movement, about what really moves the body in space when bodies, spaces and gestures really refer to the dilemmas of being human. In the *Mahabharata* we find a powerful example of a theatre of humanity that looks back to the original wound by placing it in the poetic incipit of the work. Are we today still capable of addressing the crossroads of existence around a poetic and political question? How can we approach the legacy of Brook’s story-worlding practices in the shadows of anthropogenic ecological disasters?

Between 5th and 8th October 2023, we welcomed a group of 40 eco-oriented artists, scholars, and educators from all over the world to Ostia and the Natural Reserve of the Roman Coast (Rome, Central Italy) to participate in ‘*La Selva: International Eco-Somatic and Regenerative Arts Residency*’.³ *La Selva* aimed to curate a re-discovering of the deep embodied knowledge of ecological connection within the human experience, as a necessary process of care and cultural resistance. It was a pathway for seeking a dialogue between ways of feeling the ecological crisis, as if through an underlying nostalgia, for an intense, intelligent, and poetic possibility. This article attends to the pedagogical performative investigations that tried to emerge during the residency and to the reflections and interventions that followed.

² Brook, 1996, p. 52.

³ The residency was coordinated by Raffaele Rufo and Thomas Kampe and organised in collaboration with Intercultural Roots’ (UK), Teatro del Lido di Ostia (Rome) and the Archaeological Park of Ostia Antica (Rome). As artistic director of Teatro del Lido, Flavia Gallo took part in the creative development and facilitation processes of the residency. For more details, see <https://www.raffaelerufo.com/ecosomatics/2023-la-selva-human-nature-connect-residency-rome>.

1. Is the forest dead?

RAFFAELE RUFO:

We live in the age of ecological disasters. When looking at the conditions of the land where we live and where our performance and pedagogical practice is based, the coastal area of Rome, one of the greenest urban areas in Europe, we are faced with a painful scenery of death. A great fire on 4 July 2000 burnt nearly three hundred hectares of forest and, in less than ten years, more than fifty-thousand pine trees have been killed by an insect imported from North America. One is tempted to embrace the discourse of ecological disaster as a call to action. However, apocalyptic thinking is dangerous because it reinforces the paradigm of nature as something separate from us. If we are part of nature, then ecological losses are also human losses, and our wounds are embedded in the wounds we have caused.⁴ Our ecological imagination struggles to come to terms with the fact that we are the cause of the pain that we see outside of us while at the same time not being able to disembed ourselves from the colonial and extractivist systems that sustain the reproduction of that pain. From this perspective, the emergence of non-anthropocentric creative ecologies requires going through an embodied experience of witnessing and honouring the interweaving of the human inside the natural and the natural inside the human.⁵ Where does this process of healing and regeneration start? I think that seeding reciprocity with the rest of nature requires reconfiguring our relationship with death and regaining the ability to grieve individually and collectively for ecological losses.⁶ Following this trajectory, our conversations and creative collaborations throughout the last three years have led us to approach the training of the imaginal and physical world of the performer as the recollection of an ancient resemblance and commonality with the nonhuman and with matter. How does this challenge impact the vantage point of your dramaturgical practice?

⁴ See Rufo, 2024b, for a discussion of the transformative potential of connecting our fear of ecological crises with the somatic practice-knowledge of embodied experience.

⁵ The interweaving of the perceiving self and the perceivable world was explored phenomenologically by French philosopher Maurice Merleau-Ponty (1968) in his unfinished work *Visible and Invisible* to be then integrated with ecological thinking by geophilosopher and cultural ecologist David Abram (2010; 2017). Abram proposes an immersive notion of perception structured by reciprocity and claims that we can be “taken up” in the larger and deeper perceptual terrain in which the human senses are embedded only by “rendering ourselves vulnerable” to that terrain (Abram, 2010, p. 58).

⁶ See Rufo, 2024a, for a discussion of the perceptual roots of ecological crises and the role of ecosomatic art practices as a vehicle for embodying personal and cultural processes of grieving and regeneration.

FLAVIA GALLO:

The forest is dying. And it is already dead and being reborn. All this at the same time. The fact is that we do not feel it, we are no longer witnesses or participants in these cyclical evolutions that could be a source of deep mourning, enthusiastic celebration, and lively contemplation. How exactly we humans experience this state of separation from the rest of nature today is difficult to say: poets help us find the right word to speak of this wound. Ancient Latin poets used to speak of the *selva* as a place of continuous material and immaterial fabric, the habitat of the *genius loci*, the unified cosmos of a common destiny plot shared by humanity with water, rocks, trees, and divinities. Contemporary Italian poet Chandra Candiani takes us into the forgotten fabrics of the *selva* as in a process of re-initiation:

“Dear Forest
I come to you
in search of the wound
before us.
The senses,
gentle servants,
invite out into the Open
the skinned and empty hands.

I sense the silence
that mirrors the World
And says:
I recognise you
Fragment of dust
and I give you the name.
I will call you
in the heart of my bones
In the hour
without

a home.”⁷

Naming “the fragment of dust”: what a splendid image to tell of this similarity, to tell of the lost feeling of this similarity, to tell we are not aware of the participation in the life-death-life cycle with the rest of nature; we are called to remember a technical, poetic, relational force to feel again as part of the *selva*. To do so, as Pier Paolo Pasolini, a poet dear to the territory of Ostia, would say, we need

“a mystical strength
to change the course of our lives:
we must dedicate ourselves to that cause,
like Gandhi to the Independence of India,
like Danilo Dolci
to the rebirth of Partinico.
We need protests and fasts...”⁸

Pasolini was murdered fifty years ago here in Ostia, “the periphery of the periphery” as he used to call it, in a place that has now become a kind of wild sanctuary, where human and non-human life-death-life seems to have finally intertwined around the dead body of a prophetic poet telling our contemporary stories us from the past, screaming about the desecrated/epiphanic time we are living in nowadays. Is the forest dead? Yes or no; it perhaps doesn’t matter when the fact is that its life and death do not raise action, do not inspire movement. The life of the forest is not the flesh of the contemporary world.

Embracing death and becoming intimate with it was a central issue in ancient myth. Our first conversations were around the myth of Persephone, the female archetype, queen of the underworld: she who, in the transition from the childlike state of Cora to that of Persephone's adulthood, makes us witness the possibility of crossing a threshold that we are no longer even able to trace. We wondered how it would be possible, starting from a quality of touch that ecosomatic dances are able to engage, to transfer the myth onto the plane of a collective dramaturgy, open to the

⁷ Candiani, 2023, p. 5, my translation from original Italian.

⁸ Pasolini, cited in Tuscano, 2022, n. pag., my translation from original Italian.

participation of artists and citizens, willing to narrate through their performing bodies those ancient stories that happen every day in the theatre of the world. The inability of grieving collectively for the wounds of the world has spread so powerfully in our *psyche* (read Greek: soul) that we are right in it: the coffins of the pandemic, the war-corpses on the borders of Europe, the Mediterranean *Mare Nostrum* that has become a grave. Everything tells us of a grieving that we are no longer even able to place temporally in our everyday life. Our ancestral memory has the poetic equipment to tell us what we must do, but we no longer have a sensory language that can enable us to see life-death-life as a fact of love, just like Cora who, out of love, becomes Persephone.

RAFFAELE RUFO:

I resonate with the sense of in-betweenness emerging from your account of death. When last year I was scouting the Ostia territory of the Natural Reserve of the Roman Coast in search of inspiring sites for running *La Selva* residency, I was struck by a particular place in the Forest of Castel Fusano where the traces of the great fire of 2000 are still very tangible. I was faced with a spontaneous scenography of the tragedy and touched by an ancient sense of solidarity with the dead trees. Indeed, this sense of solidarity was only deepened through the experience of being immersed in a dynamic space between life and death: where the pine trees lived (planted by humans as monoculture for commercial purposes), now the plants of the Mediterranean scrub (the “*macchia*”) are thriving again (see Figure 1).

La Selva Residency, Forest of Castel Fusano, “Field of Fire and Regeneration”
Photo by Stefania Milazzo

Death is a loss that we humans struggle a lot with. To let death become life is something that trees, and plants can do, that other species can do, and that we humans struggle with. It takes time, it takes space, it takes courage, and it takes letting go. It’s not death and life as two separate worlds. It’s death and life as continuous worlds, one interweaving into the other. We need pathways to work with these interweavings so that they become visible, so that it becomes meaningful to work with them.

2. What is *La Selva*?

FLAVIA GALLO:

There is a beautiful expression matured by Edda Ducci, the first to hold a Professorship in Philosophy of Education in Italy. Ducci defined the teaching and practice of education “as a call to existence”. She asked through what radical dynamism is someone taught to love, to enthusiastically become passionate about

something, to live their interiority, to perform a creative act, etc. and identified this dynamism as a form of “call-contagion”. A human being turns to another human being and works to get to the point of achieving a qualified intimacy with her. The conditions are thus set in which contagion can take place, those conditions, that is, in which the one called can find in herself that same dimension that is active in the other. This condition will be experienced by the “infected” person according to her own modalities and not according to the modalities proper to the other. The quality of the relationship is decisive so that something active in someone is also kindled in the other in an original way.⁹

I always need to turn my thoughts to this reasoning to protect an educational-artistic practice from the risk of wanting to induce or presuppose something pre-packaged in the sphere of human feeling. The topic of death and grieving in their eco-biographical dimension has a mystical and utopian vastness and at the same time concerns concrete attention in the minimal unity of presence. It poses a spherical, ultimate, integral question to being in the world. How have you worked, then, to make this question available to the experience of a group, of a place, of an entire community? How have you worked to call others into this dimension of learning? How have you imagined and projected the unfolding of the call-contagion forces of *La Selva* residency? I want to ask you, ultimately, what is *La Selva* and what is its radical dynamism?

RAFFAELE RUFO:

Before trying to weave the threads of how *La Selva* was brought into the world as a pedagogical participatory process, I need to introduce the growing field of ecosomatic arts practices within which this project is positioned.¹⁰ Ecosomatics emerges from the meeting of two relational paradigms. As discussed by existential philosopher and Feldenkrais practitioner Thomas Hanna in the 1970’s and the 1980’s, somatic as a quality of experience and somatics as a field are words derived from the Greek *soma*. While the body is what we observe from the outside, the *soma*

⁹ See Gallo, 2019.

¹⁰ A vast range of arts-based ecosomatic practices were documented and discussed in two recent collections: the book on ecosomatic practices and ways of thinking edited by Marie Bardet, Joanne Clavel and Isabelle Ginot and published in 2019 for the French-speaking world (Bardet et al., 2019), and the special issue on somatics and eco-consciousness of the *Journal of Dance and Somatic Practices* edited by Thomas Kampe, Jamie Mchugh and Katja Munker in 2021 (Kampe et al., 2021).

characterises the living body as an integrated physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual phenomenon observed “from the first-person viewpoint of [one’s] own proprioceptive senses”.¹¹ Ecology, a term derived from the Greek word *oikos*, meaning household, habitat, or dwelling place, is the study of how organisms interact with one another and with their environments.¹² Ecosomatic practices engage the actual, in-the-flesh sensory experience of dancers, choreographers, theatre and performance artists and other somatic artists in their entanglement with plants, minerals, water, atmospheric phenomena and biological processes as well as with cultural and political forces. We are invited to rediscover the ancient resemblance and commonality with the rest of nature by reclaiming the human biophilic propensity for engagement with every aspect of the perceptual world as sensible and sentient. I like the expression used by Francophone pioneers Marie Bardet, Joanne Clavel, and Isabelle Ginot to describe ecosomatic practice as “a way to put attention to work” and “develop approaches that take into account the relationships of co-construction and co-invention between gestures and contexts, between perceptions, thoughts and affects.”¹³

I set out to organise the *La Selva* residency less than two years after I had moved to Rome from Milan with my family - and a bit more than four years after I returned to Italy from Australia. I was driven by a desire to develop new ways of collaborating and making community with other ecosomatic artists by focusing on the key role of place, ecological drama, and cultural roots while at the same time responding to the international drive of this young and growing field.¹⁴ *La Selva* emerged through accepting my condition as a migrant and as an exile in my own country. It is fascinating for me to observe how, despite a general sense of alienation from contemporary Italian culture, I feel more grounded in doing ecosomatic work in Rome than in Milan or Berlin, or in France or in England. I think it has to do with being closer to where my ancestors come from and working in a place that I recognise as part of my 3000 years of Greek-Latin cultural heritage. I engaged *La Selva* as a step in a long-term journey of connecting with body and roots by inviting strangers to visit “my” land. This meant going through the pain of realising how

¹¹ Hanna, 1986, p. 4. See also Hanna, 1985.

¹² Bottoms et al., 2012.

¹³ Bardet et al., 2019, pp. 15-17, my translation from French original.

¹⁴ For an in-depth excursus of my ecosomatic dance practice leading to *La Selva*, see Rufo (2023a).

much of my cultural heritage has been lost but also of how much of that heritage was already incorporating colonial brutality towards people and the land.

I remember when in April 2023 I presented for the first time the *La Selva* project at the yearly participatory planning session of Teatro del Lido di Ostia. The collaboration began with a provocation: “What would happen if we included in the artistic program the many thousands of trees populating our territory as a force of cultural renewal? I was surprised by the resonance that followed. *La Selva* is the crossroads between two tensions not easily reconcilable in an international project. On the one side there is the macro tension of wanting to connect with community and land by working with the contradictions of our territory and crossing the imaginary line between beauty and corruption, past and present, city and forest, nature and culture, sociality and isolation. This involves engaging with the unique aspects of the local ecosystem to integrate them in a working methodology of embodied curation and facilitation that stretches the boundaries of traditional theatre and performance practices. On the other side, there is the micro tension of going to the roots of sensing by engaging with a slow process of attunement with the world and witnessing a shift of perception into a heightened and expanded experience of being touched and danced by the nonhuman and by matter. The meeting of these two dimensions recalls the image of the call-contagion you mentioned in your question and of other ways of conceiving and experiencing being and learning as immersion and interpenetration.

Drawing on Stefano Harney and Fred Moten’s description of the experience of black slaves being “thrown together touching each other” to be shipped to the New World, the tactile ecological interweaving of life and death of *La Selva* can be unveiled as an experience of “hapticality”.¹⁵ As an unregulated quality of human relationship and an alternative paradigm of coexistence that is “immediately social” and that exceeds “all things that were supposed to produce sentiment, family, nation, language, religion, place, home”, hapticality is “a way of feeling through others, a feel for feeling others feeling you”.¹⁶ It is when touch and movement offer themselves as a *technē* for accessing the cherished intimacy of feeling in relation that we can start to heal the wounds of separation from the rest of nature. Extending

¹⁵ Harney and Moten, 2013, esp. Chap 6.

¹⁶ Ibid. p. 98.

Harney and Moten's proposition to encompass the more-than-human ecology of perception, the question of how *La Selva* was brought into the world becomes an opportunity to explore how life feels the skin of death in a process of reciprocal embedding. The encounter with the outpouring signs of the passages between death and life both in the Forest of Castel Fusano and in the urban cultural context of Ostia becomes the bodily earthly ground for the human and the nonhuman to feel each other again.

Was the experiment successful? We witnessed a desire for slower time, more moments of listening and not doing and for more intimacy between participants and with the place as a precondition for allowing things to happen. We also witnessed the difficult, but not impossible task of creating the conditions for inviting strangers to encounter the unique eco-cultural history of the land and of learning from the freshness of their view. This translocal challenge and its transformative potential can be appreciated in the words of a local participants, written just after the residency: "You live for thirty-two years in a place, then you learn to dance with it." Another participant living in the South of Italy but originally from the United Kingdom, wrote that the gathering "re-ignited" her faith in "humAnimals' capacity for *caritas* and creative collaboration". The project is not over yet. There is more to learn by following the unfolding of the dynamics ignited, we could say, by a spontaneous act of faith.

3. Why does ecosomatics need ancient myth?

RAFFAELE RUFO:

La Selva takes roots only a few kilometres away from the place where the Latin poet Virgil describes the landing of Aeneas and the first Greeks settlers in Italy (a place known today as Capocotta). This is one of the many synchronicities that have moved our imagination to dig into the poetic connection between ecosomatic practice and the mythic language used by our pre-Christian ancestors to narrate the drama of the human-nonhuman encounter. The word *Selva* entered our conversation after attending together Sista Bramini's theatre piece "Miti d'Acqua" at Teatro

Basilica in Roma, in February 2023.¹⁷ In this work Bramini tells stories drawn from the *Metamorphoses*, an epic-mythological poem written in Latin by Ovid (43 a.C.-17/18 d.C.). Her focus is on the “aquatic” metamorphoses which include, for example, the story of the nymph *Aretusa* being transformed into a spring of water. *La Selva* is not only the topos of the experience of a group of international artists joining an ecosomatic residency in Rome, it is also an important category of Ovid’s environmental imagination.¹⁸ In the *Metamorphoses* Ovid rewrote over 250 myths from the perspective of the past and ongoing meetings between Greek and Latin cultures. For Ovid those myths were ancient and needed to be rewritten so that they could have a contemporary value. He was exiled for doing so. Why, from a poetic point of view, does the ecosomatic rediscovery of the resemblance and commonality with the nonhuman and with matter relate to ancient myth? How can ancient myth help us get to the bottom of this quest? What is the mythical core that can be associated with this question?

FLAVIA GALLO:

Myth is a metamorphic and ancient source: it is part of that imaginal reserve of the world that helps us bring the forces of the encounter between human and non-human outside the formal boundaries of ecosomatic practice and within a specific language that anticipates it in time, that precedes it because it pre-exists it. Myth is part of the epistemological code of being human: it is a narrative in which there is a trace of the readiness of all entities to move because they are touched, to touch because they are changed, to change because they are moved. It is a sound/syllabic/phonetic/semiotic and sensory 'ecosystem' often embedded in the experience of the speaker who recounted it verbally and from memory: a narrative that brought together modes of knowledge that in our techno-consumerist world are dramatically thought of separately as science, politics, and religion.

What the exact meaning of the mythical narrative was for the world that spawned it, no one can say with any precision. Seen from here, though, those ancient men and women seem to have taken it as a belief and at the same time a practical philosophy of presence: as an indication of the non-dualistic quality of human action

¹⁷ In 1992 Sista Bramini founded the theatre company O’Thiasos TeatroNatura (<https://teatronatura.it/>) which can be considered as a pioneering example of performative and pedagogical ecosomatic practices in Italy.

¹⁸ Ovid, 1986.

situated in the space between the human and the non-human. Myth reveals to us different versions of awe before all things, visible and invisible, material and immaterial, permanent and immanent. It tells us of a paradigmatic capacity of human beings to “become like” things. According to Aristotle, “becoming like” is the most intense capacity that humanity has ever possessed.¹⁹ Myth is deeply animated by this leitmotif of becoming, of being literally transformed by a feeling, of the immediate change of state at the beginning of a thought. The mythic-poetic word speaks to us of this immense reserve of multiformity that we no longer know how to access and act upon. Becoming river, rock, tree, echo, fire, star and then human again is a dramaturgy of existence constantly staged in an ancient and pregnant place of culture, where science and poetry coexisted, where nothing could be imagined outside the contiguous and interchangeable whole formed by what is animated and what is not.²⁰

The version of ancient myths recounted in Ovid's *Metamorphoses* is often the one that has found a more stable place in the memory, and that has helped myth to find a place in Western culture and history of art. The origins of these stories, however, were very ancient; many were aetiological myths (from the Gr. *aitia*, 'cause' and *logos*, 'discourse', 'tale about causes') intended to explain the origin of a name, a custom, a ritual. Within Ovid's great poem, the stories in which the protagonists leave their human appearance to transform themselves into trees or flowers number just a dozen, but some are among the most unforgettable. The first *dendromorphosis* (i.e., 'transformation into a tree') comes to us in the first book and is perhaps the most famous story of all: the myth of Apollo and Daphne (I, 452-567). Struck by Cupid's golden arrow, which he has mocked, Apollo falls madly in love with the nymph Daphne, who, on the contrary, struck by a lead arrow, detests him. So, to his advances, she flees, until, when the god is about to overpower her (it is an attempted rape, one of many in this book), she begs her father, the river Peneus, to rescue her from the outrage by means of a metamorphosis:

“Scarce had she made her prayer when through her limbs
A dragging languor spread, her tender bosom
Was wrapped in thin smooth bark, her slender arms

¹⁹ For a discussion of Aristotle's philosophy of mimesis, see Scaramuzza, 2016

²⁰ Ibid.

Were changed to branches and her hair to leaves;
Her feet but now so swift were anchored fast
In numb stiff roots, her face and head became
The crown of a green tree; all that remained
Of Daphne was her shining loveliness.”²¹

Not being able to exhaust this taxonomy of images of transformation, let us call to mind one last story that connects us more closely to the theme of grief: in Book X, the last dendromorphosis concerns the myth of Cyparous (X,106-141), another beloved of Apollo; the young man is fond of a deer of beautiful form and tame character, which he kills one day by mistake. He is so desperate that he asks the god to transform him in such a way that his weeping lasts forever. This is how the cypress (Kyparissos in Greek), the tree of mourning, came into being.²²

Through the metamorphic nucleus of ancient myth, ecosomatics can be engaged as an ancestral kinaesthetic crossing or an extended-deepened-intensified perceptiveness of the relationship between human and non-human. This is, ultimately, a way to embody the descent into the memory of the world to gather the somatic experience of myth in the movement of the body and in the movement of words.

RAFFAELE RUFO:

Both myth and ecosomatic practice foreground the radical relationality of our being. Both also affirm the intrinsic value and inherent meaningfulness of all forms of life. I too think that myth can be very useful as a gateway to reach towards a deeper experience and understanding of somatic movement by liberating the language of breath, touch, blood, and tissues from the chains of a dogmatic form of empiricism that separates movement from the spirit and the imagination. In describing the philosophy of Deep Ecology, Arne Naess talks about “breaking the chain that confines the self as separate from nature” by “listening to its silent presence” through the senses.²³ Myth can help us tell the story of the internal

²¹ Ibid., p. 17.

²² Ibid.

²³ Naess, 2008, cited in Zatta, 2023, p. 163

adventure of movement as an experience of listening and responding to the secret languages of the non-human and of matter. Classics scholar Claudia Zatta compares Naess' Deep Ecology with the metamorphic nucleus of Ovid's *Metamorphosis*. Although, she argues, both works ground transformation in the eco-relationality of being, Ovid "does not merely observe and describe the existence of natural beings *in* a system of relations; rather, he looks at their emergence *from* (a system of) relations".²⁴ The Latin poet tells us how the first laurel tree came into life *due* to relations between humans and the rest of nature. The world described in his poem "encompasses the perceptual and affective reception of the living being experiencing it".²⁵ This is a crucial passage to embed the subjective experience of ecosomatic practice in a larger scheme of things which is not defined by the human/nonhuman separation, but which rather involves our imagination in what today we would call the biosphere.

4. How can we become sensors today?

FLAVIA GALLO:

Isn't the sensorial, immersive, risk-taking, responsive human being, available to touch, to the embrace, to the metamorphic gaze of the other that provokes the change of state (*Medusa* comes to mind?) precisely the one that we could call the artist today? The one who perpetually bears witness to the presence in the human of a living sensory force that touches, moves, dances, sings and knows everything about language and its true power? The "Homo Mythicus", if one can use this name, the one who, through mimesis, can transform himself or herself into things - into water, into rock, into plant, into deities - the one who feels and transforms himself in the present moment, as in mythical stories, is disappearing. Does ecosomatics come after myth to rekindle a quality of being part of, of being-with, of co-existing? A conscious quality that is mindful of the perennial metamorphosis of things, the dance of the psyche, the acrobatics of the spirit, the embrace of the spirit that the body is?

²⁴ Zatta, 2023, p. 164.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 164.

The ancient world was filled with ritual practices that served, through a complex and layered initiatory preparation, to gain access to the sacred, by definition separate, beyond a precise threshold. The theme of approaching and preparing for the ritual (for the profound and scandalous touch) is a key to enter the space of the drama where sacrifice takes place. In order to make this crossing, it is imperative to gain certain conditions, certain ganglia of openness and awareness about bringing into play the integrity and actuality of one's world. One's whole world. Approaching: this seems to me to be a fundamental act. It means taking steps, guided by one who knows the destination, has explored it before and calls you and takes you there. It means setting out, becoming a wayfarer, making yourself a stranger in your own home. And how do I approach the sacred space, the space of ritual? What images must I encounter and embody so that a precise feeling of something to yearn for can arise, a feeling that makes me want to feel more, that awakens my desire? What do I offer sight, smell, touch, hearing, taste so that a sixth sense can act synesthetically with the others?

RAFFAELE RUFO:

As a way of awakening the metamorphic in the human and as a source of regeneration of the quality of participation, I want to draw on the stories on “becoming sensor” articulated by Natasha Myers. Myers, a critical plant scholar and cultural anthropologist with a background in biology and dance, describes her arts-based research project on plant sensing as a kinesthetic entanglement with Toronto’s High Park. She writes about an experience of “experimenting with ways to tune in to the sentience of the land and participate actively in animating its relations” and of “developing the skills that we would need in order to render ourselves available to the work of allyship”.²⁶ Myers provides another insight into the experience of “becoming sensor” by referring to the ways they “pay attention to the worlds they are actively making”.²⁷ Trees sense the world in ways that are very different from how we humans have configured the experience of sense perception for ourselves. They sense and respond to touch, smell, taste, and sound in a deep relation with other plants, animals, insects, microbes, and fungi.²⁸ In this sense their presence is “watching” us in ways we are not necessarily aware of because we have built our

²⁶ Evans, 2022, n.pag.

²⁷ Myers, 2020, n.pag.

²⁸ Ibid.

understanding of perception based on the assumed separation from the rest of nature.²⁹

In *The Elusive Obvious*, Moshe Feldenkrais, one of the pioneers of modern somatics, makes a point that is quite important for establishing the eco-soma alliance. We know the reality of the world through our five senses. One would expect most of our nerve cells to be directed towards the outside world to manipulate, analyse, and integrate this information. However, only one nerve cell per thousand informs us about the external environment. Our sensorium is much more directed towards the reality we experience on the inside than we would expect.³⁰ How can we rediscover our relationship with the external world based on the awareness that we receive so much sensory information from our internal systems, our organs, our fluids, our breath, our muscles, and our bones? With the project “Sensing with Trees” (2020-2022), which predates “La Selva”, I engaged the encounter with trees in urban parks and forests as a slow improvisational dance of listening and attunement through which the human sensorium is imbued with arboreal attention and trees are recognized and honoured as intimate companions of movement and becoming.³¹ Borrowing the words of Moshe Feldenkrais, one of the pioneers of modern somatics, this involved “reducing all stimuli to their bare minimum” to facilitate noticing and integrating the finer changes in the muscular and nervous systems.³² A key aspect of my ecosomatic inquiry in “Sensing with Trees” was to allow my body to feel movements without focusing on a particular intention, or letting other thoughts take hold. Led by my experience as a dancer, I was guided by an emergent range of somatic improvisational modes of movement and attention. What began as a series of tasks evolved into an assemblage of rituals of belonging and thanksgiving to the body and the earth. As rituals, these explorations felt strongest through the act of repetition.³³ To become sensors we need to accept the frustrations of waiting and suspending judgement. Something unexpected and

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Feldenkrais, 1981, esp. pp. 87-88.

³¹ See Rufo, 2022 and 2023b.

³² Feldenkrais, 1975, p. 2.

³³ Among these somatic improvisational modes of experiencing body and earth, wandering, lying, grounding, and shaping were the ones through which I gained the deepest insights into the reciprocity of perception between humans and trees. The internal adventure of movement involved in this research was articulated in a somatic storytelling which functions both as an account of what happened and as a guide for readers to engage sensorially with the presence of trees (see Rufo 2023a).

unintended is invited to address our conscious awareness whilst remaining outside our grasp. A porous space unfolds between the inner and outer worlds, until the sense of witnessing something outside our body and the sense of being witnessed by that presence feel nested into each other.

Working with *La Selva* participants through immersive experience has confirmed that something happens, i.e., that we are moved, when the opening proposed by ecosomatic practice meets the inner world of the participant. This is an encounter that cannot be anticipated or controlled, but that can be prepared. During the residency we have learned that the presence of performers and skilled somatic arts practitioners is not a guarantee that something meaningful dramaturgically will take place. Let's go back to what happened when the resident artists were guided into the Forest of Castel Fusano (the same referred to at the beginning of this article) to meet with burnt trees and witness the cycle of life-death-life (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: La Selva, Forest of Castel Fusano, “Shaping and Grieving Practice”
Photo by Sebastian Tilsch, 2023

As facilitator, I proposed a somatic-improvisational movement practice of sensing and grieving with the dead trees and with the land. After an initial phase of wandering the field in a process of synesthetic listening, I invited the participants to seek an intimate experience of lying on the fallen trunks and shaping into their dead bodies. I asked the participants to work on the sensation and embodied image of being touched by the trees and by the air and the light and the voice of the birds both kinesthetically and affectively. The invitation to shape human bodies into the trunks was offered as a way of acknowledging and coming to terms with how humans shaped this land anthropomorphically and exploitatively and how this played a key role in creating the conditions for the fire that burnt these trees. The process ensued in the spontaneous offer from a participant to lead a song of collective grief inspired by the Southern Italian tradition of the “*prefiche*” (singers accompanying the funeral procession). We were all gathered around the fallen trunks. After this, another participant offered a ritual of gratitude which involved the distribution of some drops of the maple syrup she had produced according to the indigenous customs of Turtle Island and brought to Rome from Canada as a gift to the land. While sharing the syrup, the participant talked about the importance of learning how to take only what is needed from trees.

After the international artists left Ostia, the presence of thousands of dead pine trees, scattered across the urban territory, still standing on their feet with their grey crowns deprived of leaves, became stronger and stronger. During the months that followed *La Selva* the municipality of Rome decided to cut down the dead trees for safety reasons. I was left to witness their felling and eradication on my own, powerless. It felt like a betrayal. I spent a lot of time reflecting on the kind of eco-cultural regeneration that could ensue by honouring the death of these trees in a shared ritual positioned between the performative and civic intervention.

In the meantime, my uncle died, and I travelled to my family’s hometown in the Cilento region near Salerno (South of Italy) to attend his funeral. It was an empowering experience. Before being locked in a coffin and taken to the church, his dead body was placed on his bed, in his room for the ritual of the wake. As I entered the room, I saw his dead body shining in the open coffin. Family members and friends were gathered around him, sitting on chairs or standing. There was a sprig of asparagus in his hands. The texture of the asparagus and of his skin felt so beautifully

attuned, as if the two were bonded in an ancient solidarity. I touched his hands and his face. There were people crying. Others were touching and kissing his face. The room felt very alive. Surrounded by a sense of affective and kinesthetic empathy, I felt that in that shared tactile experience of grieving for another human, rehearsed for thousands of years, before the advent of Catholicism, we could also learn to grieve for the sufferings imposed on other species. I started to imagine conducting an ecosomatic funeral for the felled trees. I spent months collecting what was left on the margins of the streets after the intervention of chainsaws, bulldozers, and drilling rigs: broken branches, decomposing and very fragile shields of bark perforated by insects, and fragments of the marrow shuttered at the base of the trees and once connected with the roots. These vibrant materials became an important inspiration for preparing a follow-up ecosomatic training immersion with a group of local artists.

La Selva was willingly organised in complex public sites not designed for performance pedagogical practice and with a very large group of participants. With the aim to create the conditions for intimacy and trust, I developed a more specific training process for a small group, called “Listening with the Planet”³⁴. The ecosomatic immersion was set in a more well-known, contained and rehearsed outdoor space where people are used to work pedagogically on human-nature connections: the arts-based forest school attended by my children. I placed the remains of the dead pines gathered from across the natural reserve around the lying blocks of the trunk of a tree that had just been felled. I composed the scene of the funeral of the tree before the arrival of participants: the shields of bark stacked a bit away from the trunk, the fragments of marrow wood on the soil to form a circle around the stump, a bucket of water on top of the stump, a big tray with small bits of charcoal near the water, and the broken branches on the other side of the trunk. I also placed a flute, music triangle, and a pair of wooden sticks on the trunk. I brought some poetic, reflective and philosophical texts to be offered to participants during the ritual as possible words to be spoken. Before inviting the participants to enter the scene one by one, I told them the story of the dying forest. The ritual was conducted through and as a process of improvisation and composition. After asking participants to lie on the trunk, I proposed that they engage the elements I had brought there, one

³⁴ See <https://www.raffaerufu.com/ecosomatics/masterclass>.

at a time, to build the ritual. Soon after that I witnessed quite clearly what I referred to above as the meeting between the internal world of the participant and the external world of the practice. The focus went on the large pieces of bark and one participant asked to be buried under them. The group responded with incredible care and intensity (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Ecosomatic Training, “Funeral of the Tree”
Photo by Valentina Vitolo, 2024

The funeral for the tree transformed quite spontaneously and rather quickly into a death ritual where it was hard to tell whether we humans were grieving for the death of trees or whether trees (what was left of them, their “flesh”) were grieving for the human condition (on this inversion, compare Figure 3 with Figure 2). A second threshold was reached when we all got closer to the lying participant and placed our hands on her body with that solemn attention that is reserved to the dead ones, or to the loved ones. This inspired me to mark her passage into life by playing the flute. The participants responded by starting to remove the pieces of bark from her body and by interacting vocally with the flute. This continued until the lying participant, freed from that weight, opened her eyes and was welcomed emphatically by the others. She then was helped to stand up. It was an intimate moment. The ritual ended with a verbal exchange of gratitude and with some reflections on how the ritual worked and how much we are in denial of death. The person who had been lying during the ritual concluded with a sentence that I found quite inspiring and that I will try to rephrase out of memory: We are truly taken care of when we are born and when we die; what happens in between is something else, more like a struggle.

FLAVIA GALLO:

What does it mean to participate? Who is the participant? Who can be attracted by such a proposal? Who enters the space of the collective drama, a space in which an understanding of intimacy is the alchemical basis for encountering the unknown, for going towards the unknown of the other, whether human or non-human? It is again a question of movement: going towards each other, being touched by the world, yielding to the other's proposal, welcoming the indeterminate; seeking disequilibrium by holding on to the reciprocity of the earth we share as a common ground, while assuming at the same time that the song of a bird or the smell of a berry is part of part of what is happening because something is happening to those elements too, in the reciprocity of presence. The berry is touched and the song is heard. It is not neutral; it is not empty: it is something that was not before. It is a metamorphosis of the beating of the heart, of the pacing of the breath, of the material state of all of those involved.

5. How can the poetics of myth help us rediscover the resemblance with the rest of nature?

RAFFAELE RUFO:

After the international residency we began a closer collaboration with Teatro del Lido di Ostia with the vision of developing a civic-pedagogical trajectory for *La Selva*. We invited active citizens already involved in the cultural life of the theatre to participate in a series of outdoor ecosomatic immersions in key natural-cultural places of the territory. Seven months after the residency, we returned with a small group to the Forest of Castel Fusano, in the same place visited with the international artists - the same clearing hit by the great fire of 2000 (see Figures 1 and 2). You were there with me. Before walking to the clearing, we sat down for a couple of hours in the shade under the trees in an area untouched by the fire. There I guided participants through an experiential and cognitive preparation to somatic sensing and ecological awareness through readings, stories, touch and rituals. One of the tasks involved closing the eyes and finding where the heart beats - first alone and then with a partner. This phase of preparation ended with a water ritual in which the participants were invited to follow specific gestures of ablution and to respond verbally to the effects of water with a sentence on gratitude for being alive on this earth. When this preparatory phase ended, we walked towards the site of the great fire. Upon entering the clearing, we were faced with the sacred spectacle of burnt pine trees surrounded by much smaller and lively plants. I proposed a duo-based practice of leading and being led into a synesthetic encounter with the land with the eyes closed. I asked the person with the eyes open to listen and support the wandering of the person with the eyes closed and to offer her some materic and sensorial stimuli in the process. At some key moments of the exploration, the person with the eyes open was asked to pause the walk and say: "Open your eyes and look at yourself in the mirror".³⁵ How can the poetics of myth help us interpret what happened during this experience in terms of the possible meeting between the inner world of the participants and the world of death and regeneration in which we were immersed? How can the poetics of myth help us read the difficulties of contemporary humans to engage the somatic shift from having a body (as something experienced

³⁵ The task was inspired by the "Mirror Walk" developed by Joanna Macy and Molly Brown in "The Work that Reconnects", a repertoire of facilitation strategies and tools for regeneration (Macy and Brown, 2014).

by a separate mind) to being guided by the felt sense of their body in the presence of others?

FLAVIA GALLO:

Observing unarmed the way in which these now greying giants are cut down across the streets of the urban area of Ostia, Rome's greenest coastal reserve, is truly alienating. They are cut down, without being uprooted: the base is left without the vital expression of the trunk, the height of the branches, the spread of the foliage, the tenderness of the saplings, the flexibility of the fronds. The tree, which is home to thousands of beings, is interrupted: this makes one think, metaphorically, of how men and women today suffer their poetic-imaginative *diminutio*. They are not uprooted, only severed, left in pieces, exposed without burial to vision. Befriending the metamorphic potential of ecosomatic practice required making this perceptual preconditioning on the brutal treatment of urban trees to the different scenery of death awaiting us in the burnt forest. Here trees have been severed by the untamed force of fire. One of them, in the middle of the clearing, still stands, twisted, with the other half lying at its knees. (See Figures 1 and 2) The following episode narrates of the special condition making something happen authentically, of the pot of images in which the accumulated, stagnating, still inner material is given back to movement, to life, to the risk of other possible geometries.

When we returned to the site of the fire, something happened. Something happened to the perception of the place of the human in the death of the tree and of the place of the death of the tree in the human. During the sensory walk into the clearing, one participant acted in a very unexpected manner: he destroyed the remains of the dead body of the standing tree. The tree covered by a burnt and very fragile layer of bark, which concealed its charred heart, was as if attacked by the fury of the participant who literally decorticated it, tore it to pieces, reduced it to a dust that had previously held itself together in a mortuary simulacrum, motionless and ethereal. The participant plunged his hands into the flesh of the trunk and, if his companion in the practice had not helped him contain the fury, he would have pulverised the tree in its entirety. How does one contain an explosion of such vital despair at the sight of a form? And is it really to be contained? Or is it only to be observed, like a witness who takes care of the inevitable through his gaze?

This moment, filled with what the Greeks called *Thanatos*, sees a participant completely inside the action, letting go and following his own embodied call to feel more intensely, prepared for that dramatic release, through some steps that have occurred before. We cannot know whether it was one or the other image, which was the gift through which the possibility of that strong, expressive, inescapable feeling became available. Perhaps washing his hands, or seeing the others washing their hands, or the long, meditative walk taken before entering the clearing of the dead trees. It is not known. That is, it is not a scientific fact. When this participant entered the space of the ecological drama, what did he see? His partner in the sensitive search had to lend her body, offer it as a guide and protector, willing even to defend the most scandalous action: that of the destruction of the setting prepared for the practice. Our participant destroyed the simulacrum of death because he saw something underneath, he glimpsed a depth, a deeper perspective, and he put his hands into it: he wanted to see what was next, underneath, beyond. Right? Not right? The category of judging does not help us: judging whether it was right to let him continue or even stop his act would have belied that ecosomatic correspondence between inside and outside that he had been asked to prepare for. Ultimately, we asked him to go through that process.

The assumption that the dead tree should arouse in us a meditative *pietas* proved fallacious: I "greet you, touch you, caress you and honour you"... a sequence that tumultuously gave way to another, Dionysian power. As at the origin of the drama, the participant took the cult object, the object of the sacred, the most aesthetically interesting object, and tore it to shreds: he tore apart the god that lay within the simulacrum. More than that: it would have destroyed the entire landscape of the performative had not the force specular to *Thanatos* intervened: *Eros*. Dionysus understands, tests and leads both forces. We witnessed, in just a few minutes, a splendid arc of images, of powerful embodied archetypes. *Eros* is the way: caressing, touching, tasting, provoking in the other body the raising of blood pressure, the increase of the pulse, the thickening of the skin, the moistening of the cavities in the game of touching, of smiling, of accompanying each other inside the *Selva* that seems to open and welcome.

The powerful drama of having destroyed this scenario dissolves when that participant begins to walk, move, touch and lead his partner, who has the eyes closed,

within the landscape of a death revealed and deprived of its occult power. Now the *selva* opens its clearing in the sun, in the scent, in the berries, in the opulence of spring. Everything that the power of *Thanatos* had overshadowed becomes a dance in the embrace of holding each other together, of verifying whether one is still alive after death, whether after burials someone or something still has the possibility of coming out of mourning and realising that everything is now new, free, available for initiation: for kissing, for union, for fecundation. With everything destroyed, the aesthetic, beautiful and painful scenery disappears for all, and in an act of love the idea of a regeneration of all spectators, human and non-human, is reborn. An absolute, complete, perfect mythical dramaturgy: the destroyer leads his partner to initiate herself into pleasure after mourning, in the *Eros* of the enchantress maiden who discovers and plays out her seductive power, in the initial and delicate fire of spring.

RAFFAELE RUFO:

The surprising transition from *Thanatos* to *Eros* you describe brings into play the nexus between the wounds of the separation from the rest of nature and the difficulty of feeling the intimacy and sensuality of the encounter with the human other. The reciprocity of perception with the rest of nature cannot be disentangled from human reciprocity. Where in our contemporary society can we feel an intimate connection with the human other? What are the participatory aesthetic and cultural practices we can access to learn to let go while guiding and being guided by another so that an experience of *Eros* can unfold - not a simulation of what this force could be? I arrived at ecosomatics through a profound encounter with the Argentine tango dance. Returning to the notion of hapticality introduced above, the tango dance provides participants with a tactile gateway for sensing and feeling together. The dance opens up the possibility of being touched both physically and affectively by the movement of the other. This possibility unsettles the reductive idea of one's body as a separate entity preceding the encounter.³⁶ Perceiving the carnal continuum of body and world is a key passage into ecosomatic practice. In terms of performer training, this is a door for dwelling into a deep-rooted intense perception of one's self and regaining the mythological range of possible gestures you have evoked. Another important aspect that connects tango, myth and ecosomatics is that the tango

³⁶ See my PhD thesis on touch in tango as an experience of kinaesthetic listening (Rufo 2020a, 2020b).

is something that happens between two strangers. Is not a tree the stranger par excellence, so incredibly interwoven with our breath and yet brutally excluded from the sense making of human society? The experience with the participants in the forest has taught us about the importance of working on the human basis of sensing so that a more-than-human experience of immersion can take place.

Conclusion

Paradoxically, even though today we have more means of connection, more resources, more capacity to reach each other, our ways of doing research together feel more inauthentic, constrained by obsolete models or unsuited to intercepting, in contemplation, the truth of a perceptive state, of the quality of a gesture, of haptic presence. Ecosomatics presupposes a precise offer, an exchange between inner and outer worlds towards a possible transformation. It is an attitude of reflective openness to the experience of the other. This open, creative psyche is what we can hope for through an extended aesthetic education. Returning to Brook's words, we have been seeking "poetry, nobility, beauty, magic" and we are still thirsting for a Holy Theatre to move and inspire them. But "where should we look for it? In the clouds or on the ground?"³⁷ With *La Selva* and the pedagogical interventions that followed the residency we have tried to encounter the somatic perceptiveness of the participants and co-create the conditions to regain a language that breaks, fractures, undermines the predictability of human crossings in public space. We have approached the category of the "public" as one which exceeds the urban spaces of the city and the conventional spaces of theatre to direct our ecological imagination to the forest, the river, and the sea. That is where the space of theatre can be regained today!

In 1968 Brook asked Theatre and its artists to embrace the fundamental questions that shook the conscience of humanity at the time. Today, we ask Theatre to embrace the question of how we can form an alliance with the rest of nature and nurture a cultural resistance to the global system of extractivism, consumption, and exploitation that is devastating the planet. How can the arts create, through processes of widespread facilitation, an eco-cultural awareness that regenerates the community

³⁷ Brook, 1996, p. 64

and the land? For this alliance to emerge, a community needs to be summoned to feel through the feelings of the others. In the ancient past, this convocation coincided with going to the theatre, with experiencing a deep-rooted, intense perception of oneself together with the other, just as performing artists do in order to reach an expanded, intense state of perceptiveness. This is a space in-between, a space that is not empty but a threshold in which playful vitality, contemplation of the body, and the becoming of action constitute a fabric of connectivity between the sensory experience of the individual and a felt sense of the flesh of the world.

In the perspective of immersive bodily experience as an ecological observatory of the territory, we can give new life to the relationship between word and silence, doing and not doing, presence and absence as a remembrance of our shared responsibility for future generations. We are called to explore more deeply our belonging to our territory, to the beach, to the sea, to the forest. By embracing this call, the Teatro del Lido di Ostia has become a meeting point for artists and ecologically conscious citizens, both local and international. It is through these transdisciplinary encounters that ecosomatic and dramaturgical practices can contribute to approach the defence of the commons and the critical engagement with our cultural roots as a translocal form of civic action.

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Flavia Gallo is a dramatist, lecturer in Theatre and Education and research fellow in Pedagogy of Expression at Roma Tre University. She is the author of numerous prize-winning plays awarded by, among others, Sipario Prize and European Prize for Theater and Dramaturgy Tragos, Piccolo Teatro di Milano. In 2022 she was selected as playwright for the Biennale Theatre Authors in Venice. She co-founded Humanitas Mundi Teatro, an ensemble of performance research and dramaturgical cooperation in Rome. Currently Flavia is artistic co-director at Teatro del Lido in Rome.